

ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS PRE-SOWING TREATMENTS ON GERMINATION STATUS OF *Semecarpus anacardium* Linn.Kiran S. Chatar^{1*}, S. S. Harne², H. K. Deshmukh³, V. B. Shambharkar⁴, V. V. Ujjainkar⁵, D. N. Ingole⁶ and P. R. Palaspagar⁷

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Abstract

Semecarpus anacardium L. is known as marking nut or 'Biba', important medicinal tree found in wild, having problem in seed propagation due to its hard seed coat and high oil content. The present investigation was conducted to evaluate the effect of various seed treatments on germination status. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Block Design (RBD) comprising eight treatments with three replications. The treatments included soaking seeds in cow dung slurry at 24 hours and 48 hours, GA₃ @150 and 300 ppm, 1% KNO₃, 1% Thiourea, concentrated H₂SO₄ (for 10 minutes) and seeds without any treatments. The results revealed that seed treatment T7 (concentrated H₂SO₄ for 10 minutes) significantly improved germination status of *S. anacardium*, resulted in the earliest germination (14.33 days), highest germination percentage (50.67%), and germination index (6.98) and superior seedling growth and biomass accumulation. Seed treatments with concentrated H₂SO₄ for 10 minutes showed significant results followed by seed treatments with cow dung slurry, GA₃ and KNO₃. The results concludes that acid scarification using concentrated H₂SO₄ is the most effective pre-sowing treatment for enhancing germination and seedling quality in *S. anacardium* and can be utilized for nursery practices.

Key words: biomass, GA₃, germination index, scarification, thiourea.

Introduction

Semecarpus anacardium Linn commonly known as 'Biba' in Marathi, is one of the best, versatile and most commonly used herbs as a household remedy, distributed in Sub-Himalayan region, Tropical region, Bihar, Bengal, Orissa and central parts of India. The word *Semecarpus* is derived from Greek word simeion meaning "marking" or tracing and carpus meaning "nut". Anacardium means like "cardium"; - "Heart shaped marking nut". Maharsi Charaka has categorized bhallataka as dipaniya- an appetizer, bhedaniya - accumulation breaking herb, mutra sangrahaniya - antidiuretic and kushthaghna - anti dermatosis. Bhallataka is acclaimed as a drug of choice in the treatment of piles of vata and kapha types. It has also got the potential to produce allergic manifestations through contact dermatitis. (Ashwini R, et al. 2007)

Semecarpus anacardium plant has become a wild plant, it found only in forest area and it is medium to large sized tree, 10 to 20.m. tall tree with grey bark, leaves are simple alternate obovate - oblong with rounded apex globous surface, large sized, fasciated in pubescent panicles. Fruits obliquely ovoid on oblong, 2.5 cm long, heart shaped, shining green when unripe and black when ripe, seated on a fleshy receptacle which is yellow when ripe, occurs throughout India in semi evergreen and moist deciduous forest. (Khan, 2015). The natural propagation of *Semecarpus anacardium* Linn. takes place by seeds. However, the seeds viability decreases as the time increases. Seeds are rich in oil and protein and medicinally useful.

The plant *Semecarpus anacardium* Linn can be propagated by sexual and asexual methods. Seed germination of marking nut is not even and also irregular, making sexual propagation difficult. The initial growth of seedlings is also slow and it requires about 180-240 days to attain the state of planting. Irregular germination in marking nut seeds may be due to dormancy or due to its hard seed coat. Therefore, pre-soaking treatment is very important (Preethi B, 2014). Seed dormancy and the capacity of seeds to germinate are possibly associate with the seed coat (Panda and Hazra, 2009).

The ever-increasing demand of the marking nut is noted importantly in health as well as in textile industry. Conventional propagation of *Semecarpus anacardium* by seed is difficult because of low germination frequency and poor seed viability (i.e. 32%) (Rathiesh P, et al., 2019). Day by day the quantity of this plant is decreasing, it is need to aware it's importance to society otherwise it will be become rare and we will loss one of important plant from the dictionary of Indian medicinal plants. Hence, the study was carried out on the response of the various seed treatments in Biba for, enhancing the germination potential at an early with healthy seedling production.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out during 2024-25 at Department of Forestry, Post Graduate Institute, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth Akola. Seeds of *Semecarpus anacardium* were collected from KVK, Karda District- Washim. Before sowing of seeds, the polybags were filled with the common media comprising of soil + sand + FYM in the ratio 2:1:1. The experiment was laid out in a Randomised Block Design (RBD) with eight treatments and three replications. The treatments details are as follows.

Treatments No.	Treatment Details
T1	Soaking seeds in cow dung slurry for 24 hours.
T2	Soaking seeds in cow dung slurry for 48 hours.
T3	Soaking seeds in GA ₃ 150 ppm
T4	Soaking seeds in GA ₃ 300 ppm
T5	Soaking seeds in KNO ₃ 1% for 12 hours
T6	Soaking seeds in Thiourea 1% for 12 hours
T7	Soaking seeds in conc. H ₂ SO ₄ for 10 min (followed by cold water washing)
T8	Control

The observations were recorded every day after date of sowing and recorded germination and growth of seedlings i.e. days to emergence, germination percentage and germination index. The percentage of germination was calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Germination percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of seeds germinated}}{\text{Number of seeds sown}} \times 100$$

And the Germination index was determined by using below formulae;

$$GI = \frac{X_1}{D_1} + \frac{X_2}{D_2} + \frac{X_3}{D_3} + \dots + \frac{X_n}{D_n}$$

Where, X - The number of seedlings germinated in D days taken for germination (Kumar, et al 2008).

The observations were recorded and get analyzed with the statistical tools of OPSTAT computer program. The results and interference were drawn and discussed.

Result and Discussion

The table I revealed the effects of different seed pre-treatment methods on days to emergence, germination percentage, and germination index. In the table the data clearly shows significant differences among the eight pre-sowing treatments applied to *Semecarpus anacardium* seeds. The treatment T7 (Soaking seeds in conc. H₂SO₄ for 10 min) found best regarding Days to emergence in *S. anacardium* seeds, it takes minimum days (14.33 days) to sprouting from seeds, which was

followed by T2 (Soaking seeds in cow dung slurry for 48 Hours) (16.67 Days), whereas maximum days to emergence was occur in the treatment T3 (Soaking seeds in GA₃ 150 ppm for 24 days.

Whereas, the germination of *S. anacardium* was observed maximum (50.67%) in treatment T7 (Soaking seeds in conc. H₂SO₄ for 10 min), which was followed by T2 (44.33%) and T4 (40.67%). Whereas the lowest germination of seed was observed in the treatment T3 (20.33%). Also, the germination index was observed maximum in T7 (Soaking seeds in conc. H₂SO₄ for 10 min) which is (6.98) followed by T2 (4.31) and T4 (3.96) and minimum in T6 i.e. Soaking seeds in Thiourea 1percent for 12 hours (1.16).

The overall parameters of seed germination, among all the treatments, seeds soaked in conc. H₂SO₄ for 10 min (T7) exhibited superior performance. This treatment recorded the earliest emergence at 14.33

days, the highest germination index of 6.98 and the highest germination percentage of 50.67%. This was followed by treatment T2 (Soaking seeds in cow dung slurry for 48 hours), which shows an emergence at 16.67 Days, germination index of 4.31 and having germination percentage of 44.33%. In contrast, the treatment of Soaking seeds in GA₃@150 ppm (T3) recorded lowest germination percentage (20.33%).

The enhanced germination observed in conc. H₂SO₄ treated seeds may be attribute to the physiological role of sulphuric acid in breaking seed dormancy. The findings are consistent with those reported by Preeti Bhosale (2014) which showed maximum (74.67) germination percentage recorded in acid scarification treatment and it was significantly superior over rest of treatments.

Table I: Effect of various pre-sowing treatments on seeds of *S. anacardium*.

Treatments	Treatment details	Days to emergence (Days)	Germination Percentage	Germination index
T1	Soaking seeds in cow dung slurry for 24 hours.	20.33	30.67	2.24
T2	Soaking seeds in cow dung slurry for 48 hours.	16.67	44.33	4.31
T3	Soaking seeds in GA ₃ 150 ppm	24	20.33	1.88
T4	Soaking seeds in GA ₃ 300 ppm	18.33	40.67	3.96
T5	Soaking seeds in KNO ₃ 1% for 12 hours	22.33	21.67	1.77
T6	Soaking seeds in Thiourea 1% for 12 hours	20.33	20.67	1.16
T7	Soaking seeds in conc. H ₂ SO ₄ for 10 min (followed by cold water washing)	14.33	50.67	6.98
T8	Control	20	36.33	3.19
F-test		Sig.	Sig.	Sig.
SE (m)		1.68	2.24	0.396
CD (5 %)		4.9	6.55	1.211
CV (%)		14.88	11.71	21.482

Fig 1: Effect of various pre-sowing seed treatments on days to emergence in *Semecarpus anacardium* L.

Fig 2: Effect of various pre-sowing seed treatments on seed germination of *Semecarpus anacardium* L.

Fig 3: Effect of various seed treatments on germination index in *Semecarpus anacardium* L.

Fig 4: Stages of Seedling emergence from seed of *Semecarpus anacardium* L.

Fig 5: Performance of *Semecarpus anacardium* L. seedlings under nursery condition after germination.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the findings of the investigation indicates that among the eight seeds treatments, seed treatment T7 i.e. Soaking seeds in conc. H_2SO_4 for 10 min, was the most effective in enhancing germination performance of *Semecarpus anacardium* L. This treatment resulted in the shortest time to emergence and germination, along with the highest germination percentage. The results highlight the significance of pre-sowing treatments, particularly the use of conc. H_2SO_4 helps in improving seed germination and promoting successful seedling establishment in this ecological and economically valuable species. Further, this study may helpful for better results in upcoming trials.

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